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A Survey of Robotic Competitions and its Impact in STEM and Engineering Education

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ABSTRACT

Several studies point to the need to interest child and young students in the areas of science, technology, engineering and maths (STEM).

According to the National Research Council, out-of-school programs have been shown to contribute to young people's interest in and understanding of STEM, connect young people to caring adults who serve as role models, and reduce the achievement gap between young people from low-income and high-income families. The main criteria of programs that produce positive outcomes for learners are: they are engaging, responsive, and make connections.

Research also suggests that intellectually engaging STEM programs provide young people with first-hand, materials-rich, and place-based learning opportunities that involve processes of scientific or engineering investigation and practice.

Furthermore, today's students are active learners. They construct their own knowledge structures and learning environments through interaction and collaboration. Their approach to learning is highly nonlinear rather than following the sequential structure of the typical school curriculum. They are adept at multitasking and context switching. And they are challenging the teachers/faculty to shift their instructional efforts from the development and presentation of content, and instead become like mentors and consultants to student learning.

On a more advanced level, the Educating the Engineer of 2020 report states that engineering education must be realigned to promote technical excellence as well as understanding of work strategies, team, communication, ethical reasoning, societal and global contextual analysis skills in practising engineers. This implies that, to prepare professionals to communicate with the public, engage in a global engineering marketplace and become lifelong learners, humanities, economics, political science, language, and/or interdisciplinary technical subjects must be part of the undergraduate education.

To motivate engineering undergraduates to drive their learning process it is necessary to adopt interesting methodologies, e.g., PjBL and autonomous teamwork, and problems, e.g., finding solutions for the benefit of others. The desire to find together the solution for a real world problem drives students to search for knowledge, learn complex subjects and share their findings. Such design, build and test projects are intended to provide students with an experience that is fun, motivating and educational, increasing student self-confidence and interest in learning as well as in engineering.

According to Duderstadt's report Engineering for a Changing World: A Roadmap to the Future of American Engineering Practice, Research, and Education (2008), employers increasingly seek social and cultural skills such as the ability to communicate, to function in an increasingly diverse environment, to be committed to and capable of lifelong learning, and to not only adapt to but actually drive change. This will require that engineering education shift increasingly away from the lecture-laboratory approach of the sciences to more active learning experiences that engage problem-solving skills, team building, creativity, design, and innovation. Psychologists

and cognitive scientists have known for decades that the most effective learning occurs through the active discovery and application of knowledge, not through mere study and contemplation.

Still in the same report, it is stated that follow-up studies of student achievement following participation in projects such as the solar car race or autonomous vehicle competition reveal that student academic performance improves very significantly with such experiences, even though students may temporarily take reduced course loads to accommodate such demanding activities. This could be augmented with extracurricular experiences such as co-operative education, internships, study abroad, service learning, and team experiences such as the solar car race or autonomous vehicle competition.

Furthermore, Duderstadt's still argues that all institutions, programs, and roles must strive to provide exciting, creative, and adventurous educational experiences capable of attracting the most talented of tomorrow's students.

Similar objectives are stated in "The Green Report – Engineering Education for a Changing World", from ASEE. According to it, engineering education programs must not only teach the fundamentals of engineering theory, experimentation and practice, but be relevant, attractive and connected.

Also, as addressed by some institutions, namely ABET, that argues that faculty will need to evolve from professors to learning managers, by being collaborative, having broad knowledge, and integrating coaching and counselling into teaching formats while creating new ones made possible by the students themselves, students are given some project objective and they must, by themselves, define their detailed objectives, with the teachers working as tutors and not as problem solvers.

Robotic competitions are appealing for fulfilling these tasks. These competitions "capture" and interest lots of youngsters for the technical areas, are pleasant and join education with entertainment (edutainment). Moreover, some particular competitions can foster the advance the state of the art on some specific research and development areas.

Keeping these ideas in mind, this paper introduces several studies that point to the need to transform STEM, and Engineering, Education and the requirements that should be addressed to drive this change. Based on the survey of these sources it is then suggested that this change can be conducted through robot-based competitions and are introduced several such events, directed to distinct target ages and with different platform requirements.

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